

Ontology engineering of automatic text processing methods

Zhanna Sadirmekova^{1,2}, Jamalbek Tussupov³, Aslanbek Murzakhmetov¹, Gulkiz Zhidekulova¹,
Aigul Tungatarova¹, Murat Tulenbayev¹, Shynar Akhmetzhanova¹, Zhanar Altynbekova⁴,
Gauhar Borankulova¹

¹Department of Information Systems, Faculty of Information Technology, M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University, Taraz, Kazakhstan

²Institute of Information and Computational Technologies, Committee of Science of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Almaty, Kazakhstan

³Department of Information Systems, Faculty of Information Technology, L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University, Astana, Kazakhstan

⁴Department of Computer Science, Kazakh National Women's Teacher Training University, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Article Info

Article history:

Received Apr 14, 2023

Revised May 3, 2023

Accepted May 6, 2023

Keywords:

Automatic text processing methods

Domain ontology

Ontology design patterns

Content patterns

Ontology completion

Ontology engineering

ABSTRACT

Currently, ontologies are recognized as the most effective means of formalizing and systematizing knowledge and data in scientific subject area (SSA). Practice has shown that using ontology design patterns is effective in developing the ontology of scientific subject areas. This is due to the fact that scientific subject areas ontology, as a rule, contains a large number of typical fragments that are well described by patterns of ontology design. In the paper, we present an approach to ontology engineering of automatic text processing methods based on ontology design patterns. In order to get an ontology that would describe automatic text processing sufficiently fully, it is required to process a large number of scientific publications and information resources containing information from modeling area. It is possible to facilitate and speed up the process of updating ontology with information from such sources by using lexical and syntactic patterns of ontology design. Our ontology of automatic text processing will become the conceptual basis of an intelligent information resource on modern methods of automatic text processing, which will provide systematization of all information on these methods, its integration into a single information space, convenient navigation through it, as well as meaningful access to it.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/) license.

Corresponding Author:

Zhanna Sadirmekova

Department of Information Systems, Faculty of Information Technology, M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University

60 Tole bi str., Taraz, 080000, Kazakhstan

Email: janna_1988@mail.ru

1. INTRODUCTION

Ontologies are extensively used to formalize knowledge in the areas of scientific subjects. With the aid of ontology, it is possible to assure their uniform and consistent description as well as the convenient presentation of all the required ideas of the simulated domain. A scientific subject area (SSA) is understood as a subject area (SA) that covers a specific scientific discipline or knowledge, including its objects and subjects of research, characteristics and used research methods. Currently numerous strategies and approaches are suggested to speed up the time-consuming process of developing an ontology for any topic area [1]–[4]. Accordingly, intensively developing an approach based on the ontology design patterns application (ODP) [5]–[8]. According to this approach, ODP is documented descriptions of proven solutions to typical problems of ontology modeling [9]. They are developed to assist and streamline the creation of

ontologies and aid developers in avoiding common blunders in ontology modeling. Despite the fact that using ontology design patterns reduces the need for human resources and raises the standard of ontologies being created, currently only one method for building ontologies i.e. eXtreme design methodology [10], suggested within the NeOn project [11], openly declares the use of ODP.

Note also that there are not many ontology development tools that support the use of ODP. These include, a plugin for NeOn project development tools of ontology, as well as a plugin for the web protégé ontology editor [12], [13]. However, these funds cover only a part of possible problems associated with patterns. So, there are no instruments supporting the patterns searching, construction and extraction from ontologies, and very few instruments supporting the patterns collection, discussion and also dissemination. To some extent, the latter include of ontology design patterns catalogs [14]–[17], which have also actively developed now.

The paper considers an approach to the implementation of such kind of ontology design patterns as content patterns [18], which play an important role in the development of ontologies of modern methods of automatic text processing (ATP) proposed by the authors. The ontology of ATP modern methods includes both classical ATP methods and methods using machine learning. The papers [19]–[21] existing ontologies containing ATP methods were analyzed. At the moment, there is an ontology of machine learning [22], [23] which contains a small set of ATP methods based on machine learning. However, existing ontologies cannot give an idea of the whole variety of this type of method. In addition, many new methods and models have recently appeared that have not yet been reflected in previously developed ontologies. To systematize data and information resources, to organize meaningful access to them, the ontology of the subject area “automatic text processing” developed within the framework of this paper will be used, and software basis will be used as a standard and tool of semantic web technologies [24].

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND ONTOLOGY MAIN DEFINITIONS

Let be given the SA ontology, the replenishing rules of this ontology, the syntactic and semantic model of the SA language, the terms dictionary and input data in final text form in a natural language containing information for replenishing the ontology. We consider that ontology O subject area includes the following elements: i) a finite non-empty set of classes C_o that describe the subject area concepts; ii) a finite set of data domains D_o ; and iii) a finite set of attributes with names from the set $Dat_o \cup Rel_o$, while the data attributes from Dat_o accept values from some data domain in D_o , and the values of relationship attributes from Rel_o that model relationships between classes are instances of classes from C_o .

Every class $c \in C_o$ determined by set attributes: $c = (Dat_c, Rel_c)$, where each data attribute $\alpha \in Dat_c \subseteq Dat_o$ mapped domain $d_\alpha^c \subseteq D_o$ with values in $V_{d_\alpha^c}$, and every attribute relationship $p \in Rel_c \subseteq Rel_o$ accepts values classes $c_p \subseteq C_o$. All attributes set in class c denoted as $Atr_c = Dat_c \cup Rel_c$. For attribute γ his class is denoted as c^γ and his values set as D^γ . Among class attributes, singled out non-empty of key attributes set Atr_c^K , which can be attributes of both data and relationships. Set $a = (c_a, Dat_a, Rel_a)$ is an instance of class $c_a = (Dat_{c_a}, Rel_{c_a})$ ($a \in c_a$), if and only if every attribute data in Dat_a has name $\alpha_a \in Dat_{c_a}$ with values V_{α_a} from $V_{d_{\alpha_a}^{c_a}}$, and every attribute relationship in Rel_a has name $p_a \in Rel_{c_a}$ with values V_{p_a} as instances of classes from c_p . Key attributes data are always unambiguous, i.e. every key attribute in each instance of ontology maybe have only one value. Key attribute relations correspond to bijective relations. We consider ontology without synonyms classes and attributes data, i.e. $\forall \alpha_1, \alpha_2 \in Dat_o: d_{\alpha_1} \neq d_{\alpha_2}$ and $\forall c_1, c_2 \in C_o: Atr_{c_1} \neq Atr_{c_2}$. Class c_2 inherits class c_1 if and only if $\forall a \in c_2: a \in c_1$.

Informational content IC_o ontology O ; this a set of copies classes of this ontology. Problem replenishment ontology is the calculation of informational content by given input data for a given ontology. There we define a set of A information objects (i : objects) retrieved from input data and relevant copies ontology. Every informational object $a \in A$ has a view $(c_a, Dat_a, Rel_a, G_a, P_a)$, where:

- a. Class $c_a \in C_o$
- b. Dat_o is a set of attributes data $\alpha_a = (\alpha, Val_{\alpha_a})$, where
 - Name $\alpha \in Dat_{c_a}$
 - Val_{α_a} is set of attributes data $\bar{v} = (v_{\bar{v}}, s_{\bar{v}})$, where:
 - values data $v_{\bar{v}} \in d_{\alpha_a}^{c_a}$ and $V_{\alpha_a} = \{v_{\bar{v}} | \bar{v} \in Val_{\alpha_a}\}$ and $s_{\bar{v}}$ is structural information (position in input data)

- c. Rel_a is set of attributes relations $p_a = (p, V_{p_a})$, where
- name $p \in Rel_{c_a}$
 - V_{p_a} is i - objects set of class $c_o \in c_{p_a}$
- d. G_a is grammatical information (morphological and syntactic signs);
- e. P_a is structural information (many positions in input data).

Denote a set of all attributes i -object a as $Atr_a = Dat_a \cup Rel_a$. Every i -object natural way corresponds to some instance ontology: if $a = (c_a, Dat_a, Rel_a, G_a, P_a)$ is some i -object, that his corresponding copy ontology is $a' = (c_a, Dat_{a'}, Rel_{a'})$. Every attribute $\alpha' \in Dat_{a'}$ has values $V_{\alpha'}$. Every $p \in Rel_{a'}$ has values V_{p_a} .

3. DEVELOPMENT OF ONTOLOGIES SUBJECT AREA “AUTOMATIC TEXT PROCESSING”

The ontology of “automatic text processing” subject areas as shown in Figure 1 includes the systematization of modern ATP methods, a specification of properties, relationships between them, techniques and areas of their publications, and application. Systematization of all information on the specified methods can be carried out on the next basics: by purpose (solved applied problem types), and by areas of use. The core of the ATP ontology is formed by the ATP class, which defines the main properties of the ATP methods, and its subclasses, which are used to represent the types of solutions to problems using methods. Such classes are machine translation, abstracting, annotation, sentiment analysis, rubrication, classification and text pasteurization, and building knowledge bases.

Figure 1. Ontology of the subject area “automatic text processing”

To build an ontology and its initial content, a technique was used to develop ontologies using basic ontologies that include only the most general entities that do not depend on a specific subject area and ODP [25], [26] which are documented descriptions of proven solutions to typical problems of ontology modeling in practice. The use of such patterns not only improves the quality but also greatly facilitates the development of an ontology since it can involve experts in the modeled area who do not have the skills of ontology modeling. To assess the quality of the ontology was developed a methodology [27], on the basis of which the involved experts carried out an experimental assessment of the created ontology, including an assessment of the degree of agreement of the experts. Metrics for evaluating various ontology properties that do not require expert work are also considered. As a result of the research, we propose a methodology for the development of intelligent information resource of automatic text processing (IIR ATP), it offers the architecture and algorithm for the development of IIR ATP. The principles and approaches underlying the methodology determine the following main features: i) focus on semi-formalized software; ii) independence from software; iii) focus on the maximum use of ready-made developments (both copyright and third-party); iv) use of semantic web technologies and service-oriented approach, information system supporting scientific and educational activities (ISSEA) development technologies; v) use of the ISSEA shell as a framework for

the future IIR ATP; and vi) openness and scalability of the proposed tools; convenience and low entry threshold for the use of the proposed funds. The format for describing ATP methods is supplemented with elements that serve to describe the context development and use of ODP. For these purposes, the ontology of ATP methods includes the following classes: scope, activity, task, publication, person, organization, and information resource. To associate methods with instances of these classes, the ontology of ATP includes relations that allow link ATP with SA, persons, organizations, and projects in which they are used, as well as with publications and information resources where they are described. The ontology describes most fully the ATP methods implemented in the proposed IIR ATP system [28] using the following ODP templates: structural logical patterns, content patterns, presentation patterns, and lexico-syntactic patterns (LSP) [29]–[31].

Necessity of use structural logical patterns arose due to the lack of expressive means in the web ontology language (OWL) [32] for representing complex entities and constructions that are relevant in the construction of ATP ontologies, in particular, many-place and attributed relations (binary relations with attributes), as well as ranges of valid values determined by the developer of the ontology. Pattern specialization can consist of renaming, in specifying the names and values of its properties (attributes and relations). Figure 2 shows the specialization of patterns on the example of the structural logical pattern “binary attributed relation”. The central place in this pattern is occupied by the auxiliary class Relation with attributes, with which the base classes that model the arguments of a binary relation are associated, through the relationships “is an argument” and “has an argument”. At the same time, in the pattern (in link labels) it is indicated that there should be one such argument. The attributes of a binary attributed relation are modeled by the properties of the relation class with the attributes “has an attribute” and “has an attribute from domain”. In general, such a relationship may have no attributes, as reflected in the link labels that represent those properties. The concretization (meaning) of the pattern consists in substituting specific property values into it.

Figure 2. Binary attributed relationship patterns and its specialization

The pattern “area of allowable values” is intended to set the possible values of any property of the class, when is known in advance the whole values set (usually string) and can be stated at the stage of develop. Content patterns are designed to uniform provide and consistent of concepts representation used in ATP and their properties. Content templates are to provide a uniform and consistent representation of ATP concepts and their properties. Such patterns were developed for concepts that are typical for most SSA: subject of research, object of study, section of science, task, method, scientific result, project, activity, organization, person, publication, and information resource. For each of these patterns, a set of proficiency testing questions is defined. With these questions, the optional and mandatory compositions of pattern elements ontology are identified and requirements for them are described, which are presented in the restrictions and axioms forms. For each pattern representing the concept of SA, a set of key attributes has been compiled that uniquely identify concept specific instance. Figure 3 shows a pattern for representing “ATP methods” concept. The pattern description elements are represented by the obligatory classes of the ontology task, science section, organization and person, optional classes activity, and scientific result, and the relations “solves”, “used in”, “implemented in”, and “has an author”. In pattern representing the concept of “ATP methods”, there is one key attribute “name”.

Figure 3. “Method” concept patterns

Competency examples assessment questions representing ATP methods content pattern: “what is methods name?”, “who is methods author?”, “when was method proposed?”, “what problems are solved using the method?”, “what activity uses the method?”, “in what scientific results is the method implemented?”, “who is using the method?”, “what organizations use the method?”.

4. ARCHITECTURE OF AN INTELLIGENT RESOURCE BASED ON MODERN ATP METHODS

IIR ATP consists of the following components as shown in Figure 4; an ontology of ATP methods, a repository of ATP methods, basic ontologies repository, a dictionary of scientific lexicon, data and ontology editors, a subsystem to automatic replenishment of an LSP based ontology. The repository of ATP methods is built on basis of ATP methods ontology and includes realizations of ODP. At the same time, structural-logical patterns presentation patterns, content patterns are implemented by OWL language means, while LSP is presented in a description language on specialized template [33].

The automated ontology building system (AOBS) supports the building methods of SSA ontology based on basic ontologies that contain the most general concepts that are typical for most SSA. For this reason, the system consists of a repository of basic ontologies such as: scientific knowledge ontology, scientific activity ontology, the basic ontology of problems and basic ontology of information resources [34]. All base ontologies have characteristics in OWL language. Content patterns have been developed and included in the ATP repository for the most important basic ontologies concepts. The developed ontology model was implemented in the Protégé 5.5.0 ontology editor, Figure 5.

Figure 4. Architecture of the automated ontology building system

Figure 5. Protege editor

The system includes data editor for convenient use of ATP methods, that enables replenishing the ontology of the SSA by concrete definition of content patterns included in ATP methods repository. The dictionary of scientific lexicon contains semantically marked terms used in scientific texts to describe the essence of various ATP methods. It is used to extract subject vocabulary from texts and automatically generate an SA dictionary, as well as for subsequent automatic text analysis using LSP. The subsystem of automatic ontology replenishment is intended to enter information extracted from texts in natural language into SSA ontology. For this, LSP is used, built on content patterns basis and general scientific lexicon dictionary intelligent information resource is designed to systematize information about modern methods of automatic text processing and provide meaningful access to it. The work of the resource is organized on ATP ontology basics, which is its conceptual basis.

The left side of Figure 6 shows the class hierarchy of the ATP ontology. The right side shows a description of the ATP method, which includes the name of the method, a description of its purpose, a link to the OWL view, a link to a graphical representation, a set of questions for assessing competence, and links to projects in which it was developed and used. In addition, IIR ATP is an AOBs user interface that provides users with access to all repositories and editors that support the development of the SSA ontology, as well as the subsystem of automatic ontology replenishment based on LSP.

Figure 6. Intelligent information resource

5. CONCLUSION

This paper describes the ontology model of an intelligent information resource developed by the authors according to modern methods of automatic text processing. The ontology systematizes information about the area of knowledge “Automatic text processing” and provides developers of IIR ATP with a single conceptual basis. The Ontology Design Patterns used in this approach appeared as a result of solving ontology modeling problems that the authors of the paper encountered in the process of developing ontologies for various scientific subject areas. The use of ontology design patterns makes it possible to provide a uniform and consistent representation of all the entities of the scientific subject areas of ontology, to reduce the number of errors in ontology modeling, to increase the “comprehensibility” of the ontology by developers, and thus to provide the possibility of collective development of ontologies. Since the use of Ontology Design Patterns greatly simplifies and facilitates the development of the ontology of the scientific subject areas, it can involve experts in a particular scientific subject area who do not have the skills of ontology modeling, which can significantly speed up the development of the ontology. Our further research is aimed at the full-scale implementation of the subsystem for automatic ontology replenishment based on lexico-syntactic patterns.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was funded by a grant for Financing scientific and technical projects for 2022-2024, from the Science Committee of the Ministry of Science and higher education of the Republic of Kazakhstan, grant number “AP14972834”, (Grant No. AP14972834).

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Benarab, J. Sun, F. Rafique, and A. Refoufi, “Global ontology entities embeddings,” *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, pp. 1–12, 2023, doi: 10.1109/TKDE.2023.3235779.
- [2] A. De Nicola and M. Missikoff, “A lightweight methodology for rapid ontology engineering,” *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 59, no. 3, pp. 79–86, Feb. 2016, doi: 10.1145/2818359.
- [3] S. Arsovski, B. Markoski, P. Pecev, D. Lacmanović, and N. Petrovački, “Advantages of using an ontological model of the state development funds,” *International Journal of Computers, Communications and Control*, vol. 9, no. 3, pp. 261–275, Apr. 2014, doi: 10.15837/ijccc.2014.3.260.
- [4] Y. Zagorulko and O. Borovikova, “Technology of Ontology Building for Knowledge Portals on Humanities,” in *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (including subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, vol. 6581, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2011, pp. 203–216.
- [5] Y. A. Zagorulko, O. I. Borovikova, and G. B. Zagorulko, “Application of ontology design patterns in the development of the ontologies of scientific subject domains (in Russian),” in *Data Analytics and Management in Data Intensive Domains: XIX International Conference*, 2017, pp. 332–340.
- [6] A. Gangemi and V. Presutti, “Ontology design patterns,” in *Handbook on Ontologies*, 2009, pp. 221–243.
- [7] A. Sattar, E. Salwana, M. Nazir, M. Ahmad, and A. Kamil, “Comparative analysis of methodologies for domain ontology development: a systematic review,” *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 99–108, 2020, doi: 10.14569/IJACSA.2020.0110515.
- [8] M. N. Asim, M. Wasim, M. U. G. Khan, W. Mahmood, and H. M. Abbasi, “A survey of ontology learning techniques and applications,” *The Journal of Biological Databases and Curation*, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1093/database/bay101.
- [9] A. Bogdanchikov, D. Ayazbayev, and I. Varlamis, “Classification of scientific documents in the Kazakh language using deep neural networks and a fusion of images and text,” *Big Data and Cognitive Computing*, vol. 6, no. 4, 2022, doi: 10.3390/bdcc6040123.
- [10] E. Blomqvist, K. Hammar, and V. Presutti, “Engineering ontologies with patterns - the eXtreme design methodology,” *Ontology Engineering with Ontology Design Patterns*, pp. 23–50, 2016.
- [11] “NeOn project,” NeOn Project, 2018. http://neon-project.org/nw/Welcome_to_the_NeOn_Project.html (accessed Feb. 17, 2022).
- [12] “A free, open-source ontology editor and framework for building intelligent systems,” *Protégé*. <http://protege.stanford.edu/> (accessed Feb. 18, 2022).
- [13] K. Hammar, “Ontology design patterns in WebProtégé,” in *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 2015, vol. 1486.
- [14] S. Sandugash, T. Jamalbek, S. Madina, Y. Akbota, and A. Ainur, “Building a standard model of an information system for working with documents on scientific and educational activities,” *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 445–455, 2021.
- [15] L. Dodds and I. Davis, “Linked data patterns: A pattern catalogue for modelling, publishing, and consuming linked data,” 2022. <http://patterns.dataincubator.org/book> (accessed Feb. 21, 2022).
- [16] “Ontology design patterns (ODPs) public catalog,” ODPs, 2009. <http://odps.sourceforge.net> (accessed Feb. 25, 2022).
- [17] Z. Sadirmekova, A. Yerimbetova, and A. Ibraimkulov, “Development of an information model of the portal of scientific knowledge by means of semantic web technology,” in *2022 7th International Conference on Computer Science and Engineering (UBMK)*, Sep. 2022, pp. 182–187, doi: 10.1109/UBMK55850.2022.9919463.
- [18] V. Presutti, E. Daga, A. Gangemi, and E. Blomqvist, “Extreme design with content ontology design patterns,” *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, vol. 516, pp. 83–97, 2009.
- [19] V. S. Sadanand, K. R. R. Guruvyas, P. P. Patil, J. J. Acharya, and S. G. Suryakanth, “An automated essay evaluation system using natural language processing and sentiment analysis,” *International Journal of Electrical and Computer Engineering (IJECE)*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 6585–6593, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijece.v12i6.pp6585-6593.
- [20] T. Gherasim, M. Harzallah, G. Berio, and P. Kuntz, “Methods and tools for automatic construction of ontologies from textual resources: a framework for comparison and its application,” in *Studies in Computational Intelligence*, vol. 471, Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013, pp. 177–201.

- [21] O. Zhezherun and M. Ryepkin, "Automatic generation of ontologies based on articles written in Ukrainian language," *NauKMA Research Papers. Computer Science*, vol. 5, pp. 12–15, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.18523/2617-3808.2022.5.12-15.
- [22] J. Braga, J. L. R. Dias, and F. Regateiro, "A machine learning ontology," Preprint, *Frenxiv*, vol. 5, pp. 2–10, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.31226/osf.io/rc954.
- [23] J. Luo, D. Yu, and Z. Dai, "A latent dirichlet allocation and fuzzy clustering based machine learning model for text thesaurus," *International Journal Of Computers Communications and Control*, vol. 15, no. 2, pp. 1–16, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.15837/ijccc.2020.2.3811.
- [24] "W3C." <https://www.w3.org/Consortium/membership.html> (accessed Jan. 19, 2022).
- [25] B. T. Victorovna, T. S. Zhaksylykbayevna, M. F. Alexandrovich, Y. A. Sembekovna, S. S. Kairolliyevna, and B. A. Muratovna, "Link grammar parser for Turkic languages and algorithms for estimation the relevance of documents," in *2016 IEEE 10th International Conference on Application of Information and Communication Technologies (AICT)*, Oct. 2016, pp. 1–4, doi: 10.1109/ICAICT.2016.7991663.
- [26] A. E. Misnik, "Metagraphs for ontological engineering of complex systems," *Journal of Applied Informatics*, vol. 17, no. 2, pp. 120–132, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.37791/2687-0649-2022-17-2-120-132.
- [27] A. G. Batyrkhanov, Z. B. Sadirmekova, M. A. Sambetbayeva, A. N. Nurgulzhanova, Z. S. Ismagulova, and A. S. Yerimbetova, "Development of methods and technologies for creating intelligent scientific and educational internet resources," *Bulletin of Electrical Engineering and Informatics*, vol. 11, no. 5, pp. 2968–2977, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.11591/eei.v11i5.3075.
- [28] S. Belov, D. Zrelava, P. Zrelav, and V. Korenkov, "Overview of methods for automatic natural language text processing," *System Analysis in Science and Education*, no. 3, pp. 8–22, Sep. 2020, doi: 10.37005/2071-9612-2020-3-8-22.
- [29] R. De Almeida Falbo, "SABiO: systematic approach for building ontologies," in *CEUR Workshop Proceedings*, 2014, vol. 1301.
- [30] A. Fedotov, V. Barakhnin, A. Murzakhmetov, and I. Milyuk, "Modelling of process information dissemination and its impact dynamics to mass consciousness," *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Information Technology*, vol. 98, no. 23, pp. 3691–3702, 2020.
- [31] A. Murzakhmetov, A. Dyusembaev, U. Umbetov, M. Abdimomynova, and K. Shekeyeva, "Study of the innovations diffusion on the base of naming game mathematical model," *CompuSoft*, vol. 9, no. 1, pp. 3547–3551, 2020, doi: 10.6084/ijact.v9i1.1036.
- [32] G. Antoniou and F. van Harmelen, *Web ontology language: OWL BT - handbook on ontologies*. 2004.
- [33] Z. H. B. Sadirmekova, J. A. Tussupov, M. A. Sambetbayeva, A. S. Yerimbetova, and Y. A. Zaeorulko, "Features of the development of intelligent scientific and educational internet resources," in *2021 6th International Conference on Computer Science and Engineering (UBMK)*, Sep. 2021, pp. 389–394, doi: 10.1109/UBMK52708.2021.9558999.
- [34] E. Sidorova, "Ontology-based approach to modeling the process of extracting information from text," *Ontology of Designing*, vol. 8, no. 1, pp. 134–151, 2018, doi: 10.18287/2223-9537-2018-8-1-134-151.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Zhanna Sadirmekova holds a Ph.D. in Information Systems from L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University, Astana, Kazakhstan. Successfully defended her thesis on "Development of technology for integration of information systems to support scientific and educational activities based on metadata and ontological model of the subject area". She is currently pursuing postgraduate studies at the Federal State Autonomous Educational Institution of Higher Education "Novosibirsk National Research State University" in Physics and Astronomy. Currently, she is Associate Professor of Information Systems Department at M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University, Taraz, Kazakhstan. Research interests: information technology in education, artificial intelligence, search, digital library, ontology. She has more than 50 publications. h-index 3. She can be contacted at email: janna_1988@mail.ru

Jamalbek Tussupov Doctor of Physical and Mathematical Sciences, place of defense - Kazakh National University, specialty code-01.01.06 "Mathematical logic, algebra and number theory". Dissertation topic: "Problems of definability and algorithmic complexity of relations over algebraic structures". Has over 100 publications, including: 1 manual; 4 monographs; 30 articles in journals of Scopus, 30 articles in journals of the list of COXON and VAK of the Russian Federation; 5 certificates on official registration of computer programs used in teaching and research practice, and h-index 5. He can be contacted at email: tussupov@mail.ru.

Aslanbek Murzakhmetov received Ph.D. degree in 2022 from al-Farabi Kazakh National University in specialty Information Systems. Currently, he is Associate Professor of Information Systems Department at M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University, Taraz, Kazakhstan. He has more than 20 scientific papers. He was a junior researcher at Al-Farabi KazNU and local coordinator of the LMPI project of the Erasmus+ program at Dulaty University. Research interests: pattern recognition and classification; optimization systems, big data processing, multi-agent systems, stochastic programming methods, methods of operations research. He can be contacted at email: aslanmurzakhmet@gmail.com.

Gulkiz Zhidekulova candidate of technical sciences, currently, she is Associate Professor of Information Systems Department at M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University, Taraz, Kazakhstan. She has more than 110 scientific papers, including 4 papers in Web of Science and Scopus rating publications, 2 monographs, 7 textbooks and 2 copyright certificates of intellectual property. H-index-1. She was the executor of the project of search and initiative research work on the topic “Development of software” Unified information retrieval system of electronic archive “for the State Archive of Zhambyl region”. She can be contacted at email: gul2006@mail.ru.

Aigul Tungatarova defended her Ph.D. thesis at the Altynsarin National Academy of Education, Astana. Currently, she is an Associate Professor of the Department of Information Systems of M.Kh Dulaty Taraz Regional University, Taraz, Kazakhstan. Research interests: information technologies in education, information security, information protection, methods of teaching disciplines of the specialty. She has more than 100 publications, including 12 articles in the journals of the Scopus, 11 articles in the journals of the Higher Attestation Commission of the Republic of Kazakhstan; H-index-2. She can be contacted by e-mail: at.tu@mail.ru.

Murat Tulenbayev Doctor of Technical Sciences, Professor of Information Systems Department at M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University, Taraz, Kazakhstan. He has more than 113 scientific papers. Research interests: digital filtering and information processing (including wavelet technologies), information and measurement systems, computer simulation and process management, environmental monitoring information systems, information technologies in education (including distance education technologies). He can be contacted at email: mtulenbayev@mail.ru.

Shynar Akhmetzhanova candidate of technical sciences, currently, she is Associate Professor of Information Systems Department at M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University, Taraz, Kazakhstan. She has more than 100 scientific papers, including 2 papers in Web of Science and Scopus rating publications, 2 monographs, 2 textbooks and 2 copyright certificates of intellectual property. She can be contacted at email: shina_70@mail.ru.

Zhanar Altynbekova is a 2nd year doctoral student at the Kazakh National Pedagogical University for Girls 8D01502- Informatics. Has more than 15 scientific works, including 2 works published in Web of Science and Scopus rating publications. Research interests: open education system. Department of Informatics and Applied Mathematics, Almaty, Kazakhstan. She can be contacted by e-mail at janka1930@mail.ru.

Gauhar Borankulova candidate of technical sciences, Associate professor and Head of Information Systems Department at M.Kh. Dulaty Taraz Regional University. She has more than 60 scientific papers, including 7 works in the rating publications Web of Science and Scopus, h-index-2. Research interests: fiber-optic technologies, microprocessor systems, information systems. Department of Information Systems, Faculty of Information Technology. Taraz, Kazakhstan. She can be contacted at email: b.gau@mail.ru.